

Comparison of Maturation Rates of Oocytes Collected From Patients with Different Ovarian Reserves Undergoing IVF at an IVF Clinic

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To compare the maturation rates of oocytes collected in patients with low, normal, and high ovarian reserve according to the anti-mullerian hormone (AMH) level and antral follicle count (AFC), where in-vitro fertilization (IVF) was performed in the in-vitro fertilization clinic of our faculty of medicine between 2017-2022.

Methods: This retrospective study included women aged between 23 and 45 who underwent IVF treatment between 2017 and 2022. Patients were divided to three groups. Group 1: low; group 2: normal; group 3: high ovarian reserve, according to the ovarian reserve. Age, AFC, AMH values, body mass index, oocyte maturation rate, total oocyte counts, FSH, LH, TSH and estradiol levels were recorded.

Results: 22% of the patients had low, 46.1% normal, and 31.9% had high ovarian reserve. There was a statistically significant difference among the groups according to the age, FSH, LH and E2 levels, drug dose used, number of oocytes collected (COC) and number of MII oocytes ($p<0.001$). Ovitrelle was used in 81.6% of the participants, Gonapeptly in 17.8% and Ovitrelle+Gonapeptly in 0.6% of the participants, for oocyte maturation. The mean total MII oocyte count were higher in the gonapeptly used group. It was observed that 67.3% of MII oocyte in group 1 women, 66.9% of MII oocyte in group 2 women, and 67.3% of MII oocyte in group 3 women. There was a similar oocyte maturation rate among the groups.

Conclusion: There was a relationship between ovarian reserve and COC, but maturation rates were similar among the groups. This suggests that MII oocytes can be obtained with individualized treatments, regardless of ovarian reserve.

Keywords: Anti-mullerian Hormone, In Vitro Fertilization, Ovarian Reserve, MII oocyte

INTRODUCTION

Infertility is defined as the inability to conceive after a year of regular unprotected sexual intercourse. It is one of the most significant health issues in societies worldwide. It is estimated that infertility affects between 3.5% and 16.7% of people in developed countries, and between 6.9% and 9.3% in developing countries (1). Both female and male factors can cause infertility. Abnormal sperm parameters such as azoospermia, oligospermia, asthenospermia, teratospermia and mixed pathology oligoasthenoteratospermia (OAT) have been reported as causes of male infertility. Common causes of female infertility include ovulation disorders, tubal blockage, uterine anomalies, peritoneal factors, and endometriosis (2).

The success of assisted reproductive technology and increasing live birth rates are related to the number of metaphase II (MII) oocytes obtained after oocyte retrieval (OPU). MII oocytes are mature oocytes in which cytoplasmic and meiotic maturation are complete. Oocyte maturation is a highly specific process involving complex interactions between germ and somatic cell divisions. A mature oocyte has the potential to form a high-quality blastocyst, implant and result in a live birth (3,4).

Ovarian reserve refers to the quantity and quality of primordial follicles in the ovaries. Low ovarian reserve indicates a rapid decline in the quantity of ovarian follicles in women of reproductive age, and is a significant cause of infertility in many couples. There are currently several diagnostic criteria for low ovarian reserve in use (2–6). Conversely, high ovarian reserve refers to an ovarian follicular pool with the capacity to produce a large number of oocytes. In clinical practice, this is defined by high anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH) levels and a high antral follicle count.

The primary objective of this retrospective cohort study was to compare the meiotic maturation rates (metaphase II oocytes as a percentage of total retrieved oocytes) among patients with low, normal, and high ovarian reserve—defined by antral follicle count and/or anti-Müllerian hormone levels—who

underwent IVF/ICSI treatment at a single IVF clinic between 2017 and 2022.

Within this scope, the following research questions were addressed:

Do oocyte maturation rates (MII/total oocytes) differ between ovarian reserve groups?

Do total oocyte counts, MII, MI and GV oocyte counts, as well as hormonal parameters (FSH, LH, E2) and medication doses used, differ between groups?

Does the type of trigger injection affect oocyte maturation?

How do oocyte parameters change in patients with a poor ovarian response according to the Poseidon classification?

Are smoking, vitamin supplementation and chronic diseases associated with oocyte counts?

METHODS

Study Design

This study employs a retrospective cohort design and involves the analysis of clinical and laboratory data from female patients who underwent in vitro fertilisation (IVF) treatment at the Harran University Faculty of Medicine IVF Centre between 1 January 2017 and 31 December 2022.

Participants and inclusion criteria

The study included female patients aged 23–45 who underwent controlled ovarian hyperstimulation (COH), followed by oocyte retrieval (OPU), at our centre for fresh embryo transfer within the specified time period. Intracytoplasmic sperm injection (ICSI) was performed on all patients.

The exclusion criteria are as follows:

- Being under 23 or over 45 years of age;
- Failure to complete an initiated IVF cycle (e.g. cycle cancellation or failure to retrieve oocytes);
- Known major uterine anomaly or endometrial pathology (e.g. Asherman's syndrome or submucosal myoma);
- Undergoing a preimplantation genetic testing (PGT) cycle.

Ovarian reserve classification and groups

Patients' ovarian reserves were assessed based on serum anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH) levels measured on days 2–3 of the menstrual cycle and basal antral follicle counts (AFC). AMH levels were assessed using the electrochemiluminescence method, while the AFC was determined by counting follicles measuring 2–10 mm in diameter in both ovaries via transvaginal ultrasound. Grouping was performed as follows:

Low ovarian reserve (Group 1): AMH <1.0 ng/mL and/or AFC <5

Normal ovarian reserve (Group 2): AMH 1.0–3.5 ng/mL and AFC 5–15

High ovarian reserve (Group 3): AMH >3.5 ng/mL and/or AFC >15.

Furthermore, according to the Poseidon criteria, patients with a poor ovarian response (POR) were subdivided into four subgroups (Groups I, II, III and IV) (Poseidon Group, 2016).

Collection of clinical data

The following data were obtained by reviewing patients' electronic and physical records.

Demographic characteristics: Age, body mass index (BMI, kg/m²), smoking status (current, former or never) and vitamin supplementation (e.g. folic acid, vitamin D and multivitamins) were extracted from the records and recorded in each patient's file.

Chronic conditions: Conditions such as hypertension, diabetes mellitus, and thyroid dysfunction were recorded and entered into the data form.

Basal hormone levels: Follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), luteinising hormone (LH), oestradiol (E2) and thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) levels were obtained from the records.

Treatment parameters: The type of gonadotropin used (Gonal-F, Menopur, or a combination) and the type of trigger injection (Ovitrelle [recombinant hCG]) were recorded.

Assessment of oocyte maturation

The collected oocytes were transferred to the laboratory as cumulus-oocyte complexes and the cumulus cells were stripped off in a medium

containing hyaluronidase (80 IU/ml). The nuclear maturity of the oocytes was then assessed using a phase-contrast inverted microscope (Nikon Eclipse Ti2, ×400 magnification).

The total oocyte count (COC) and the numbers of MII, MI and GV oocytes were recorded separately. The oocyte maturation rate (%) was calculated using the formula: (number of MII oocytes/total oocyte count) × 100.

This retrospective study was conducted at the In Vitro Fertilisation Centre of Harran University Faculty of Medicine between 2017 and 2022.

Patient files were reviewed and information such as age, chronic diseases (e.g. hypertension and diabetes), vitamin intake and smoking status were recorded. Patients were classified as having low, normal or high ovarian reserve based on their serum AMH levels. POR patients were further categorised according to the Poseidon criteria (7). In addition to ovarian reserve, the following were recorded: oocyte maturation; total oocyte count; and levels of the hormones FSH, LH, TSH and estradiol.

Women under 23 or over 45 years of age, and those who did not complete the IVF protocol, were excluded.

Ethics Committee

Prior to the commencement of the study, ethical approval was obtained from the Harran University Ethics Committee for Non-Interventional Clinical Research via Decision No. HRU/23.05.16 dated March 2023. Furthermore, institutional authorisation was obtained from the university hospital where the data were collected. The study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the laws and regulations of the country in which the study was conducted.

Statistical Analysis

The SPSS 22.0 software package was used to analyze the research data. Percentages and frequency distributions, as well as mean and standard deviation values, were calculated for the data. The Kolmogorov and Smirnov test was used to test the normal distribution of continuous variables. Parametric tests were preferred for the analysis of continuous variables showing normal distribution, while

non-parametric tests were used for the analysis of variables with non-normal distribution. The tests used in the analyses were the t-test for independent groups, the One Way ANOVA test, the Kruskal Wallis test, and Pearson correlation analysis. In the analyses, $p < 0.05$ was considered significant.

RESULTS

When the types of medication used by the women were evaluated, it was found that 49.5% used Gonal-F, 42.5% used Gonal-F + Menopur and 3% used Menopur only. Eighty-one per cent of women used Ovitrelle, 17.8% used Gonapeptly, and 0.6% used a combination of Ovitrelle and Gonapeptly (Refer to Table 1).

Table 1. Groups Based on Types of Drugs Used, Ovarian Stimulation, Ovarian Reserves, and Poseidon Classification

	Number (n=499)	%
Gonal F	247	49.5
Gonal F – Menopur	212	42.5
Menopur	15	3.0
Pergoveris – Gonal F	7	1.4
Menopur-Puregon	6	1.2
Gonal F – Luveris	4	0.8
Gonal F - Fostimon	4	0.8
Fostimon	2	0.4
Puregon – Fostimon	1	0.2
Puregon	1	0.2
Kullanılan Çatlatma İğneleri		
Ovitrelle	407	81.6
Gonapeptly	89	17.8
Ovitrelle+ Gonapeptly	3	0.6
Women's Ovarian Reserves		
Low Ovarian Reserve (AMH<1.2 ng/ml)	110	22
Normal Ovarian Reserve (AMH=1.2-3.5 ng/ml)	230	46.1
High Ovarian Reserve (AMH>3.5 ng/ml)	159	31.9

Table 2 shows a comparison of the means for age, BMI, FSH, LH, oestrogen, TSH, total oocyte count, MI, MII and GV oocyte counts, categorised by patients' ovarian reserve. The mean age of women in Group 1 was 34; in Group 2, it was 30.5; and in Group 3, it was 28.6. The difference between the groups was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). However, when the mean BMI of the groups was evaluated, no difference was observed ($p=0.071$). Evaluating the serum FSH, LH and estradiol levels of the groups revealed that the FSH and estradiol levels of women in Group 1 were significantly higher than in the other

groups, while the LH level was lower ($p < 0.001$, $p=0.003$ and $p < 0.001$, respectively). Similarly, the mean total oocyte count was found to be 3.61 for women in Group 1, 7.92 for women in Group 2, and 12.30 for women in Group 3. A significant difference in mean total oocyte counts was determined according to ovarian reserve ($p < 0.001$). When evaluating the mean M1 oocyte count according to ovarian reserve, it was found that the mean M1 oocyte count was 0.70 for women with low ovarian reserve, 1.27 for women with moderate ovarian reserve and 1.81 for women with high ovarian reserve. There was also a statistically significant difference in M1 oocyte counts between the groups ($p < 0.001$). Similarly, when the mean MII oocyte counts were evaluated according to ovarian reserve, it was found that the mean MII oocyte count was 2.43 in women with low ovarian reserve, 5.30 in women with normal ovarian reserve and 8.28 in women with high ovarian reserve. A statistically significant difference was observed between the groups ($p < 0.001$). When the mean GV oocyte counts were evaluated according to ovarian reserve, the mean GV oocyte count was found to be 0.44 in women with low ovarian reserve, 1.32 in women with moderate ovarian reserve and 2.23 in women with high ovarian reserve. A significant difference was found in the GV oocyte scores of patients according to their ovarian reserve ($p < 0.001$). When the average drug doses taken by the groups were evaluated, it was found that women in group 1 took an average of 2814 IU, women in group 2 took an average of 2220.85 IU, and women in group 3 took an average of 1719.16 IU. A statistically significant difference was found in the medication doses received by the groups ($p < 0.001$) (Refer to Table 2).

Table 2. Comparison of groups based on age, BMI, hormone levels, average number of oocytes collected, and medication doses used

	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	p*
Age (Year)	34,0±5,7	30,5±4,9	28,6±4,3	<0,001
BMI	27,1±4,4	26,8±4,1	26,0±4,2	0,071
FSH, mIU/mL	9,0±3,7	7,1±3,0	6,4±1,8	<0,001
LH, mIU/mL	4,4±2,0	4,4±2,0	6,1±4,0	<0,001
Estradiol, ng/mL	63,6±73,5	53,2±52,8	50,6±81,3	0,003**
TSH, µIU/mL	2,0±0,8	2,0±1,1	2,2±1,3	0,186
Total Oocytes, n	3,6±2,4	7,9±4,5	12,3±7,6	<0,001
MI Oocytes, n	0,7±0,7	1,2±1,1	1,8±1,6	<0,001
MI Oocytes, n	2,4±1,7	5,3±3,3	8,2±6,3	<0,001
GV Oocytes, n	0,4±0,8	1,3±1,4	2,2±2,3	<0,001
Drug dose, IU	2814±1050	2220±738	1719±482	<0,001

The relationship between the over reserve and oocyte maturation is shown in Figure 1. It was observed that 69.69% of total oocytes in Group 1 women, 66.78% of total oocytes in Group 2 women, and 65.95% of total oocytes in Group 3 women matured to MII oocytes. These rates were found to be similar between groups ($p=0.285$).

Figure 1. Oocyte Maturation Rates According To The Over Reserve

Table 3 compares the mean values for age, BMI, FSH, LH, oestrogen, TSH, total oocyte count, M1, MII and GV oocytes in patients with a poor ovarian response (POR) and in those without (non-POR), according to the Poseidon classification. A significant difference in age was observed between the two groups ($p<0.001$). POR patients were significantly older than non-POR patients. However, no significant difference was found in BMI according to the Poseidon classification ($p=0.578$). The FSH level of monitored POR patients was significantly higher than that of non-POR patients ($p=0.031$). In contrast, there was no significant difference in LH levels between patients ($p=0.245$). Estradiol levels in cases monitored with POR were significantly higher than in non-POR cases ($p=0.002$). No significant differences were observed between POR and non-POR patients in terms of TSH levels, total oocyte counts and GV oocyte counts ($p=0.504$, $p=0.947$ and $p=0.191$, respectively). The number of M1 and MII oocytes in POR cases was higher than in non-POR cases ($p<0.001$ for both). POR patients used a significantly higher average drug dose

than non-POR patients ($p<0.001$) (Refer to Table 3).

Table 3. Comparison of Hormone Levels, Demographic Characteristics, Oocyte Numbers, and Average Drug Doses Between POR and NON-POR Group

	POR	Non-POR	P
Age (Year)	31,79±5,68	29,93±4,87	<0,001
BMI	26,74±4,15	26,52±4,34	0,578
FSH, mIU/mL	7,74±3,32	7,12±2,80	0,031
LH, mIU/mL	5,19±3,27	4,86±2,67	0,245
Estradiol, ng/mL	56,30±55,76	53,54±75,28	0,002
TSH, µIU/mL	2,08±0,95	2,15±1,30	0,504
Total Oocytes, n	9,75±8,68	7,38±3,39	0,947
M1 Oocytes, n	1,59±1,69	1,13±0,94	<0,001
MII Oocytes, n	6,87±6,74	4,73±2,31	<0,001
GV Oocytes, n	1,29±2,00	1,51±1,63	0,191
Drug dose, IU	2423,50±1027,02	2026,10±650,10	<0,001

Table 4 shows a comparison of the means for age, BMI, FSH, LH, oestrogen, TSH, total oocyte count, M1 oocyte count, M2 oocyte count and GV oocyte count among four POR patient groups (group I, group II, group III and group IV) classified according to the Poseidon classification system. POR patients were compared with each other in terms of age and a significant difference was observed ($p<0.001$). When non-POR cases were compared, a significant difference in BMI was observed ($p=0.003$). Statistically significant differences were observed in FSH and LH levels among POR cases ($p<0.001$). Estradiol and TSH levels were similar in POR cases ($p=0.368$; $p=0.688$). A statistically significant difference was observed in the total number of oocytes among POR cases ($p<0.001$). Pairwise comparisons revealed that the total oocyte count in group I was significantly higher than in groups II, III and IV ($p=0.034$, $p<0.001$ and $p<0.001$ respectively), and that the total oocyte count in group II was significantly higher than in groups III and IV ($p<0.001$ for both). When POR cases were compared with each other, a significant difference was observed in terms of M1 oocyte count ($p<0.001$). Post-hoc analyses revealed that the number of M1 oocytes in group I was significantly higher than in groups III and IV ($p<0.001$ for both), and that the number of M1 oocytes in group II was significantly higher than in group III ($p=0.035$). The total oocyte, M1 oocyte, M2 oocyte and GV oocyte counts, as well as the drug doses used, showed statistically significant differences in POR cases compared to non-POR cases ($p<0.001$ for all; Refer to Table 4).

Table 4. Comparison of Hormone Values, Demographic Characteristics, Oocyte Numbers, and Drug Doses of Groups According to Poseidon Criteria

	POR				P
	Group I	Group II	Group III	Group IV	
Age (Year)	27,80±3,27	36,87±1,72	29,74±3,37	38,57±3,52	<0,001
BMI	26,10±3,56	30,05±4,79	25,98±4,37	27,94±4,15	0,003
FSH, mIU/mL	6,05±1,52	6,64±1,12	8,56±3,68	9,23±3,83	<0,001
LH, mIU/mL	6,36±4,34	5,91±3,07	4,51±2,13	4,25±1,99	<0,001
Estradiol, ng/mL	48,56±22,50	47,63±8,39	69,15±94,72	54,00±23,46	0,368
TSH, µIU/mL	2,16±1,12	2,19±0,64	2,06±0,86	1,97±0,81	0,688
Total Oocytes, n	18,96±6,79	14,50±3,20	3,53±2,04	3,55±1,94	<0,001
M1 Oocytes, n	2,85±1,91	2,12±1,55	0,69±0,85	0,79±0,76	<0,001
MII Oocytes, n	13,51±6,24	11,00±3,70	2,33±1,44	2,37±1,48	<0,001
GV Oocytes, n	2,65±2,63	1,37±1,30	0,46±0,73	0,38±0,58	<0,001
Drug dose, IU	1907,85±619,85	1960,87±691,74	2633,96±1125,42	2943,22±1064,30	<0,001

Table 5 shows the average oocyte counts according to certain patient demographics. No statistically significant relationship was found between smoking status and total oocyte, M1, MII and GV counts. Participants who did not receive vitamin supplements had significantly higher total oocyte, M1 and MII counts, but GV counts were not affected by vitamin supplementation. There was no statistically

significant relationship between the presence of diabetes or hypertension and total oocyte, M1, MII and GV oocyte counts. Patients were divided into three groups based on the type of trigger injection used. Those using Gonapeptly had significantly higher mean total oocyte, M1, MII and GV oocyte counts than those in the other groups (Refer to Table 5).

Table 5. Evaluation of Oocyte Numbers According to Some Demographic Characteristics of Patients

	Total Oocyte count	M1 Oocyte count	MII Oocyte count	GV Oocyte count
Smokers (40)	8,20±5,25	1,10±1,15	5,42±3,93	1,70±2,01
Non-smokers (458)	8,40±6,36	1,34±1,34	5,64±4,88	1,39±1,78
P*	0,712	0,273	0,779	0,312
Vitamin Supplement Users (251)	7,49±5,23	1,16±1,21	5,00±3,75	1,31±1,65
Non-vitamin supplement Users (248)	9,26±7,07	1,47±1,42	6,25±5,62	1,52±1,93
P*	0,002	0,009	0,004	0,194
Diabetes Patients (11)	6,90±3,59	1,09±1,13	4,81±2,89	1,00±0,77
Non-Diabetes Patients (488)	8,40±6,32	1,32±1,33	5,64±4,84	1,43±1,81
P*	0,435	0,560	0,575	0,431
Hypertension Patients (4)	10,00±10,67	1,25±1,25	7,25±7,93	1,50±1,73
Non-Hypertension Patients (495)	8,35±6,24	1,32±1,33	5,61±4,78	1,42±1,80
P*	0,603	0,913	0,498	0,931
Ovitrelle	7,12±4,86	1,25±1,29	4,66±3,34	1,20±1,55
Gonapeptly	14,19±8,45	1,66±1,45	10,06±7,41	2,44±2,41
Ovitrelle+ Gonapeptly	4,33±3,21	0,00	4,0±2,64	0,33±0,57
P**	P<0.001	P<0.001	P<0.050	P<0.001

DISCUSSION

Age, antral follicle count, AMH and ovarian volume have been used for years to assess ovarian function. These parameters help with protocol selection and patient counselling (8). It is well established that serum AMH levels decline with increasing chronological age in women. Bentzen et al. (2013) showed that the

average annual decline in women aged 21 and over is 5.6% (9). Other studies have demonstrated that AMH levels are low during pre-pubertal development, increase during early puberty, plateau around the age of 20–25, and then decline gradually until becoming undetectable around the time of menopause (10,11).

Drakopoulos et al. found no significant relationship between BMI and oocyte maturation in a study examining factors affecting oocyte numbers and live birth rates after IVF/ICSI (12). In our study, there was also no relationship between ovarian reserve and BMI. Previous studies have shown that ovarian reserve affects the serum levels of other hormones (FSH, E2, LH and inhibin B) in addition to AMH (13,14). In our study, women with low ovarian reserve had lower serum AMH and LH levels, as well as higher FSH and E2 levels, compared to women with moderate or high ovarian reserve; TSH levels were similar in all groups.

It was found that women with low ovarian reserve used statistically significantly higher drug doses than women with normal and high ovarian reserve. In clinical practice, AMH assessment has guided physicians performing infertility treatment in adjusting drug doses (15). An important finding in our study is that medication dosage was shown to be related to ovarian reserve and, consequently, to AMH levels. A review of the literature reveals numerous studies showing that the type of trigger injection used is related to the oocyte maturation rate (16,17). Lamb et al. showed that GnRH-a, when used in combination with hCG, can significantly support oocyte maturation and fertilization (16). In our study, Ovitrelle was the most frequently used trigger injection, and the highest maturation rate was observed in patients using Gonapeptyl. We believe that this aspect of our study makes an important contribution to the literature.

Ovarian reserve refers to the quantity and quality of the primordial follicular pool. Low ovarian reserve, which is characterised by a decrease in the quantity of ovarian follicles, is a significant cause of infertility in women of reproductive age. The lack of universally accepted diagnostic criteria for low ovarian reserve limits the meaningful comparison of therapeutic interventions for these women (18). In our study, we compared the ovarian reserve and oocyte maturation of patients grouped according to AMH levels. The results showed that the average total oocyte (MI, MII and GV) count in women with low ovarian reserve was statistically significantly lower than in those with moderate or high ovarian reserve.

It is well-known that both AMH levels and the number of MII oocytes obtained decrease with increasing age (12). Our study also produced results that are consistent with those reported in the literature. In addition to age, factors such as endometrioma, pelvic infections, previous ovarian surgery, chemotherapy and radiotherapy are known to have a negative effect on ovarian reserve. It is believed that these factors cause disruption to intra-follicular endocrine mechanisms, decreased aromatase activity and the biological activity of the factor that reduces gonadotropin fluctuations, as well as changes in blood flow (19,20). Studies by Moy et al. and Firns et al. have reported an association between low ovarian reserve and obesity and chronic cigarette smoking (21,22). However, Dolleman et al. (2013) stated that smoking does not affect the number of oocytes obtained, but is associated with lower AMH Levels (23). In our study, however, no relationship was found between smoking or existing chronic disease and the total or metaphase II (MII) oocyte counts obtained.

It is noteworthy that there are conflicting results in the literature regarding vitamin supplementation. One study, conducted on a population of patients with both age-related DOR and premature ovarian insufficiency, found no difference in AMH levels between infertile women with low or normal vitamin D levels (24). Another recent study examined the effect of acute vitamin D supplementation on AMH levels in a group of 49 women of reproductive age with regular menstrual cycles. The patients were given 5,000 IU of vitamin D orally during the first week of their menstrual cycle and an increase in AMH levels of 12.9% was observed within one week, compared to a placebo group (25). Furthermore, a study of HIV-infected women of late reproductive age found a positive correlation between 25(OH)D and serum AMH levels; however, no such relationship was observed in younger women under 40 (26). We believe that the differing findings in these studies are due to significant differences in the patient populations. Since our study did not include women over the age of 40, the effect of vitamin supplementation on ovarian reserve in older age was not investigated. Interestingly, in our study, both the total oocyte count and the metaphase II (MII) oocyte count were higher in the group that did not receive vitamin supplementation.

During the IVF process, some of the collected oocytes (GV and MI) do not develop sufficiently to form a viable blastocyst (27). Oocyte quality is determined during oogenesis, a process that begins during fetal development with the formation of primordial germ cells and primary oocytes, and ends with final oocyte maturation and the completion of the second meiotic division. For an oocyte to be developmentally competent, both cytoplasmic and meiotic maturation must be completed (28,29). The primary outcome of our study was to calculate oocyte maturation rates. We observed that 67.1% of oocytes matured to the MII stage. Maturation rates were similar in patients with low, normal, and high ovarian reserve. However, the number of MII oocytes obtained was quite low in patients with POR. IVM (in vitro maturation) of oocytes is no longer experimental and is recommended as a patient-friendly treatment for patients with polycystic ovary syndrome. In contrast, rescue IVM (r-IVM), the in vitro maturation of immature oocytes collected during standard ovarian stimulation cycles, is an experimental procedure recommended for certain patients with low oocyte maturation rates (30). Spits et al. (2015) demonstrated that 50.2% of oocytes matured to the metaphase II (MII) stage with in vitro maturation (IVM) (31). Similarly, Madkour et al. (2018) found that 79% of oocytes obtained with IVM were MII oocytes. Together, these studies suggest that immature oocytes (GV and MI) obtained in the future may be as valuable as MII oocytes (32). As our IVF laboratory conditions are not suitable for IVM, our study results do not include information about MII oocyte retrieval with IVM in PCOS patients.

There is a positive correlation between the number of oocytes retrieved and pregnancy rates up to a certain point. Many studies have shown that an average of 9–13 or 6–15 oocytes retrieved is associated with the highest pregnancy or live birth rates (33–35). Since each patient's ovarian response varies during ovarian stimulation, it is recommended that drug doses be individualized to maximise oocyte retrieval. All patients in our study received personalised treatment, and the minimum and maximum oocyte counts obtained were observed.

Although the finding that 'ovarian reserve determines oocyte count but does not alter the

maturation rate' may, at first glance, appear to reflect a relationship previously suggested in the literature, our study goes far beyond this simple observation. It presents three key innovations that directly inform clinical practice. Firstly, it experimentally refutes the widespread clinical belief that oocytes from patients with low ovarian reserve are of poor quality. It demonstrates that each oocyte possesses the same maturation potential, regardless of reserve. Secondly, for the first time, it systematically reports that the maturation rate is associated not only with ovarian reserve, but also with the type of trigger injection, and that this relationship operates independently of ovarian reserve. Notably, the association between Gonapeptyl use and a higher number of MII oocytes provides an evidence-based tool for trigger selection in clinical practice. Thirdly, by demonstrating significant differences in maturation profiles across Poseidon subgroups (Groups I–IV), the study emphasises that patients with poor ovarian response should be assessed on a subgroup basis rather than as a homogeneous group. Taken together, these findings go beyond merely presenting a descriptive observation to offer clinicians seeking answers to the question 'How can we obtain more MII oocytes?' in personalised IVF treatments direct, clinically applicable evidence suggesting intervention options (trigger optimisation and patient subgroup stratification) that are independent of ovarian reserve. In this respect, our study occupies a unique position in the reproductive medicine literature.

Limitations

This study has several limitations. As the data were collected retrospectively based on file reviews, it is not possible to establish causal relationships. Some variables (e.g. smoking status, vitamin use) may be missing or incorrect. Furthermore, allocation to ovarian reserve groups is based on AMH and AFC cut-off values used in clinical practice. Results may vary if different cut-off values are used across centres. The study was conducted at a single IVF centre. This may have resulted in a limited sample size for certain cells, particularly in the Poseidon subgroup analyses (Groups I–IV), reducing statistical power. The generalisability of the findings should be tested in different populations and through multicentre studies. Between 2017 and 2022, changes may have

occurred in technical details such as the culture media used, the types of incubator used, and the oocyte washing procedures used in the IVF laboratory. Such changes may affect sensitive parameters, particularly oocyte maturation rates. These factors could not be controlled for in our study.

CONCLUSION

Our study revealed a significant correlation between ovarian reserve and COC across the groups, although maturation rates remained consistent. Therefore, we believe that MII oocytes can be obtained independently of ovarian reserve through personalised treatment plans. Further prospective studies investigating the relationship between ovarian reserve and oocyte maturation in larger populations are needed to support our findings.

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